

The Knowledge Management Effect on Organizational Innovation of Indonesia's

Telecommunications Industry: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to perform a literature review on the linkage between Knowledge Management (KM) and Organizational Innovation (OI) in the telecommunications industry, more specifically the case of Indonesia. Applying a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach, we considered publications on Academic a research database such as Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, and Emerald Insight published in between 2015-2025.

The results reveal that KM is essential to make any types of innovation—not only product and process innovation, but also market and organizational innovation—possible, since it promotes the creation, transfer, and application of knowledge. However, while agility, collaboration, and innovation capacity are more and more enhanced through the introduction of KM in Indonesian telecommunications organizations such as telecommunication, there are roadblocks to the implementation of KM, such as disparate systems and a lack of predetermined formal process. Other factors – particularly organizational culture, leadership, absorptive capacity and dynamic capabilities – are also important in metabolizing KM to innovation. This review emphasizes the importance of more empirical studies on KM maturity models in emerging markets, and the need to combine KM frameworks with digital transformation in the context of the Indonesian telecommunications sector.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Organizational Innovation, Telecommunications Industry, Indonesia, Systematic Literature Review

1. The Impact of Knowledge Management on Organizational Innovation in Indonesia's Telecommunication Sector

Currently, the telecommunications industry is facing tight competition due to the development of technology and digitalization. Indonesia is no different and given its large and still untapped population, the industry is expected to have an upward trajectory trend as the vast populous ready up and adapt the digital era. According to the Badan Pusat Statistik the telecommunications sector generated IDR 883.68 trillion of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in the fourth quarter of 2023, a 7.74 percent increase comparing to the same period last year. This expansion reflects that the national economy is supported by its this sector (Muhammad Ilham Pratomo, 2024).

The Indonesian telecommunications landscape is highly fragmented with many local companies and few international companies; the major players have their own structure of cell towers. The leading telco operators of Indonesia are PT Telkom Indonesia (Persero) Tbk (Telkom), PT XL Axiata Tbk and PT Indosat Tbk. A few players in the Indonesian telecom sector have made themselves felt in the international telecommunication arena (Muhammad Ilham Pratomo, 2024).

The dynamic nature of telecommunications industry especially emerging markets, like Indonesia, demands continuous innovation to keep from losing competitive edge. This OI spans product development, marketing initiatives and, in turn, organizational innovations (OI). According to the *Oslo Manual (Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development – OECD, 2005)*, OI involves the adoption of new organizational methods in a company's business practices, workplace organization, or external relationships. This definition encompasses three primary dimensions:

- 1) Business practices (new methods for organizing routines and procedures);

- 2) Workplace organization (new ways of distributing responsibilities involving employees); and
- 3) External relations (new ways of organizing relations with other firms or public institutions).

Heidi Armbruster, 2008 categorizes OI into *structural OI* and *procedural OI*. *Structural OI* changes responsibilities, accountability, command-and-control systems, and information flows as well as the number of or division of functions (R&D, production, HR, finance, etc.). *Procedural OI* impacts the practices, routines and operations in a company, to change or introduce new procedures and operations.

Heidi Armbruster, 2008 further differentiates OI into *intra-organizational* and *inter-organizational* dimension, with intra-organizational innovations occurring within a company and inter-organizational innovations extending beyond a firm's boundaries (see examples in Figure 1. An Item-oriented typology of organizational innovations)

According to Nonaka, 1995, Innovation emerges through the dynamic interplay between tacit and explicit knowledge, progressing through Socialization, Externalization, Combination, and Internalization (SECI). Organizations that efficiently handle conversion of knowledge (from tacit to explicit) are more likely to innovate. KM represents a systematic approach aimed at capturing, structuring, managing, and disseminating knowledge within a company, facilitating more efficient operations, the application of best practices, and cost reduction.

Although it is widely accepted by the world that KM is important to foster innovation, very few studies have been conducted in the local context to examine the effect of KM practices on firm innovation in the Indonesian telecommunication sector. It is hoped that this study can contribute to bridging this gap by conducting a systematic review of the available literature on KM and OI in the context of Indonesia's telecommunications industry.

2. Research Questions

This review addresses the following research inquiries:

- 1) How does KM affect OI?
- 2) How is KM implemented in the Indonesian telecommunications industry?
- 3) How does KM impact the Indonesian telecommunications industry's OI?

3. Methodology

This study applies a systematic literature review (SLR) to the analysis of knowledge management and organizational innovation in Indonesian telecommunication Industry. We found related papers by searching on in Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and Research Gate using keywords: "Knowledge Management", "Organizational Innovation", "Telecommunication", and "Indonesia". The search strategy was limited to research manuscripts in peer review journals and publications during the period 2015-2025, in English or Bahasa Indonesia. Eligibility criteria Studies needed to explicitly discuss the role of KM in promoting innovation outputs but were not subjected to precise definition. Exclusion criteria excluded non-peer-reviewed articles, conference paper and unrelated topics. Data were extracted on authors, year of publication, study methods, setting, and main results. The KM-innovation relationship was discussed, interpreted and patterns perceived using thematic analysis. The data is then visualized in the VOS Viewer software.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Visualization

1. Network Visualization

Network Visualization displayed through VOSviewer is a visual representation of the interconnectedness of concepts in scientific literature, with nodes and lines connecting terms that frequently appear together. Each node represents a keyword or concept that is often the focus of study, while the size and thickness of the line indicate the strength of the relationship between the concepts. In the context of exploring the Knowledge Management System, this visualization illustrates the

intellectual landscape of the relationship between knowledge management and Organizational Innovation at PT Telkom Indonesia.

Source: Author Data Processing 2025

Picture 4.1. Network Visualization

In this graph, nodes (dots) represent keywords, while connecting lines (edges) indicate the relationship or association between these keywords based on the frequency of occurrence generated by Vosviewer.

There are two main clusters that are distinguished by the colors of the red cluster and the green cluster.

1. The red cluster is centered on keywords such as knowledge management, implementation, company, innovation, case study, and Indonesia. This shows that this group of words often appears together and focuses on case studies of knowledge management implementation in Indonesian companies with PT. Telkom Indonesia being one of the objects that are often mentioned.

2. The green cluster is dominated by keywords such as employee performance, knowledge sharing, organizational culture, and knowledge. This cluster refers to aspects of

organizational behavior and culture in the implementation of knowledge management, and how it affects employee performance.

It can be concluded that keywords in the Red Cluster such as the implementation of Knowledge Management which is a systematic process used by an organization to manage good knowledge with the aim of increasing organizational value have a relationship and an impact on employee performance, employee knowledge in an organizational culture, especially at PT Telkom Indonesia.

2. Overlay Visualization

The Overlay Visualization in VOSviewer displays the temporal distribution of keywords in the literature, colored by year of appearance.

Source: Author Data Processing 2025

Picture 4.2. Overlay Visualization

The image above is an overlay visualization generated by the VOSviewer software and illustrates the temporal development of keywords that frequently appear in the literature related to knowledge management. This visualization provides information on research trends based

on the average year of appearance of each keyword, with a color spectrum from blue to yellow representing the period from 2020 to 2022. Yellow keywords indicate newer and relatively current topics, while blue indicates topics that have been widely discussed in the past.

From this visualization, keywords such as PT. Telkom Indonesia, and Innovation are dominated by the color yellow, indicating that the focus of research on this object has become a relatively new topic and has increased in the last two years. This indicates an increase in attention to contextual studies and empirical studies based on local cases in Indonesia in the field of knowledge management.

Meanwhile, keywords such as research, knowledge management, employee performance, knowledge, knowledge sharing, and organizational culture are colored blue to purple, indicating that these topics have been discussed earlier in previous research and are relatively well-established.

3. Density Visualization

Source: Author Data Processing 2025

Picture 4.2. Density Visualization

The density visualization generated by VOSviewer in the figure illustrates the network of concepts related to the topics of knowledge management, innovation, and organizational culture. Several main clusters were identified, with keywords such as "knowledge management," "knowledge sharing," "organizational culture," and "innovation" standing out as the center of the network. The density of the color in the area indicates the intensity of the relationship or the frequency of occurrence of these concepts in the literature or data analyzed. The first dominant cluster is related to "knowledge management" and "knowledge sharing," indicating that these two concepts are often discussed together in the context of the case study conducted, especially at PT Telkom Indonesia. This indicates the importance of knowledge sharing practices in improving organizational performance. Meanwhile, the second cluster centered on "organizational culture" and "innovation" reflects the close relationship between a supportive organizational culture and the company's ability to innovate. The darker color in this area indicates that these topics have significant weight in the analysis.

4.2 Influence of KM on OI

Dr. Muhammad Arif, 2021 observed that numerous researchers argue that KM positively impacts organizational innovation across various sectors, including manufacturing, banking, automotive, healthcare, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), software companies, and diverse business sectors and industries (see more details in Table 1. Impact of knowledge management on innovation). Furthermore, different KM processes can contribute to OI (see details in Table 2. Knowledge Management Processes and Innovation (Dr. Muhammad Arif, 2021)). However, KM alone is insufficient to drive innovation within organizations. Other elements such as organizational culture, leadership and strategy, dynamic capabilities, absorptive capacity, boundary-spanning, individual creativity, knowledge worker intelligence, and organizational structure and demographics are all vital for leveraging KM to foster various types of innovation.

4.3 KM Implementation in Indonesia's Telecommunications Sector

Most studies indicate that the Indonesian telecommunications industry primarily implements knowledge sharing and knowledge storage as their KM processes (Achmad Ghazali, 2017; Aliya Rhamadhona Dinata, 2024; Ade Irma Susanty, 2016; Mariah Rabiatal Qibtiyah, 2018; Dina Fitria Murad, 2018).

For instance, PT Cellular Tbk (Cellular) utilizes KM initiatives to enhance daily operations and workforce development (Achmad Ghazali, 2017). PT. Telekomunikasi Indonesia International (Telin) conducts regular sharing sessions and has established a dedicated KM portal (Dina Fitria Murad, 2018). PT Telkom Indonesia has initiated a program called "Innovation Day," comprising talk shows, seminars, and short courses on specific topics, designed to encourage active participation from the audience to apply the knowledge gained and innovate. This program is accessible not only to PT Telkom Indonesia employees but also to the public, featuring experts from diverse backgrounds to broaden knowledge horizons (Aliya Rhamadhona Dinata, 2024).

Nevertheless, several challenges persist in the implementation of KM within Indonesia's telecommunications sector. For example, Cellular operates two KM portals, one for people development and another established in 2006 that has not been maintained. This creates a potential for KM systems to be developed in silos, which hinders collaborative workflows and processes essential for effective information and knowledge transfer. Such barriers may lead to inefficient business operations or decision-making due to repeated mistakes or risks taken, as crucial knowledge (such as lessons learned and expertise) is not shared across the organization (Achmad Ghazali, 2017). In Telin, despite there being scheduled sharing meetings, sharing practice is unplanned and offers no focus. The KM portal is standardized and accessible only for permanent employees and the HR department does not

control the use of documented knowledge from other / new employees (Dina Fitria Murad, 2018).

According to Mariah Rabiatal Qibtiyah, 2018, the implementation of KM in knowledge sharing is not optimal as it lacks formal rules or procedures that would encourage sharing activities to become obligatory for all employees. To promote a knowledge-sharing culture, building social trust is essential. A high degree of social trust may contribute to a positive attitude toward knowledge sharing behavior, but not unless this receives additional support from conveying positive value and habit regarding the behavior.

4.4 KM's Impact on the OI of Indonesia's Telecommunications Sector

According to Librita Arifiani, 2019, KM serves as a crucial driver of service innovation. The KM process encompasses the creation, sharing, and application of knowledge to generate new ideas and innovations in alignment with market demands. Effective KM results in:

- 1) Enhanced organizational agility: enabling firms to adapt quickly to technological changes;
- 2) Improved collaboration: facilitating knowledge flow between internal units and external partners
- 3) Increased Innovation Capacity: supporting development of new service offerings and customer experiences

KM not only supports innovation, but also sustains competitive advantage by promoting continuous learning and adaptation to market dynamics, leveraging big data analytics to discern market trends and customer needs, thus allowing companies to maintain a competitive edge by offering differentiated, high-value services.

5. Conclusion and Future Research

KM positively influences OI across various sectors and types of industries, including manufacturing. However, it is insufficient on its own to foster innovation within organizations.

Other critical factors—such as organizational culture, leadership and strategy, dynamic capabilities, absorptive capacity, boundary-spanning, individual creativity, knowledge worker intelligence, and organizational structure and demographics—are necessary to capitalize on KM for diverse innovations (Dr. Muhammad Arif, 2021).

Although KM practices, such as knowledge sharing and storage, have been initiated within Indonesia's telecommunications sector, they are not yet optimally maintained (Mariah Rabiatal Qibtiyah, 2018). When managed effectively, KM can profoundly impact service innovation, enhancing organizational agility, improving internal and external collaborations, and facilitating the development of new service offerings and customer experiences (Librita Arifiani, 2019).

Future research should focus on conducting more empirical studies within Indonesia's telecommunications sector, exploring KM maturity models tailored for emerging economies, and integrating KM frameworks with assessments of digital capabilities.

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Tables

Table 1. Impact of knowledge management on innovation (Dr. Muhammad Arif, 2021)

Criterion	Mediator	Predictor	Context	Source
Organizational Innovation	Organizational Learning	KM	Iranian agricultural bank	(Bagher Asgarnezhad Nouri, 2017)
	IT application, organizational capabilities		Iranian software development companies	(Mahdi Hemmati, 2016)
	Corporate culture		Taiwanese manufacturing industries	(Ru-jen Lin, 2012)
	External knowledge acquisition	Social intelligence (social awareness, social understanding, social interactions)	Australian non-profit organizations	(Kong, 2015)
	Capacity for internal assimilation, capacity for internal sharing, coordination among R&D personnel, communication fluency among R&D personnel	External knowledge acquisition	Spanish innovative technology-based firms	(Mercedes Segarra-Ciprés, 2013)
	Information technology capability	Knowledge conversion, knowledge protection	Malaysian Multimedia Super Corridor	(Abang Azlan Mohamad, 2017)
	Knowledge creation	Knowledge sharing	Portuguese companies – footwear, textile, moulds, metallurgy, information technologies, automotive components, plastics, chemicals, paper and	(Vítor Costa, 2016)

			cardboard, and ceramics.	
	Knowledge application	Knowledge sharing	Chinese firms	(Yuan Li, 2009)
	Reverse knowledge transfer	Multi-nationality, internal social capital, external social capital	Spanish multinational companies	(Daniel Jiménez-Jiménez, 2014)
	Top management support, employee involvement, continuous improvement, customer focus	Knowledge creation, knowledge storage, knowledge transfer, knowledge application	Taiwanese high-tech companies	(Richard Yu-Yuan Hung, 2010)

Table 2. Knowledge Management Processes and Innovation (Dr. Muhammad Arif, 2021)

KM Process	Innovation	Context	Source
Knowledge Acquisition, Knowledge Sharing, Knowledge Application, Knowledge Creation	Product, marketing, process, and organizational innovation	Iranian alloy steel supply chain	(Chaghoshi, 2017)
Knowledge Acquisition, Knowledge Sharing, Knowledge Creation, Knowledge Storage	Product, marketing process and organizational innovation	Jordanian manufacturing and service organizations	(Mahmoud M. Migdadi, 2017)
Knowledge Acquisition, Knowledge Sharing, Knowledge Utilization	Organizational innovation	Jordanian enterprises and consulting firms	(Bader Yousef Obeidat, 2016)

KM Process	Innovation	Context	Source
Knowledge Acquisition, Knowledge Application, Knowledge Absorption, Knowledge Organization, Knowledge Storage	Organizational innovation	Iranian sports employees	(Sepahvand M., 2015)
Knowledge Sharing	Organizational innovation	Spanish SMEs	(Pedro Soto-Acosta, 2017)
Knowledge Acquisition, Knowledge Creation, Knowledge Integration, Knowledge Diffusion, Knowledge Storage	Organizational innovation	German corporations	(Peter Pawlowsky, 2012)
Knowledge Creation, Knowledge Integration, Knowledge Diffusion, Knowledge Storage	Organizational innovation	Taiwan High-tech firms	(Ru-jen Lin, 2012)

Figures

Figure 1. An Item-oriented typology of organizational innovations (Heidi Armbruster, 2008)

		Focus of Organisational Innovation	
		Intra-Organisational	Inter-Organisational
Type of Organisational Innovation	Structural Innov.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-functional teams • Decentralisation of planning, operating and controlling functions • Manufacturing cells or segments • Reduction of hierarchical levels • ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation/networks/alliances (R&D, production, service, sales, etc.) • Make or buy/Outsourcing • Offshoring/relocation • ...
	Procedural Innov.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team work in production • Job enrichment/job enlargement • Simultaneous engineering/concurrent engineering • Continuous Improvement Process/Kaizen • Quality Circles • Quality audits/certification (ISO) • Environmental audits (ISO) • Zero-buffer-principles (KANBAN) • Preventive maintenance • ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Just-in-time (to customers, with suppliers) • Single/dual sourcing • Supply Chain Management • Customer quality audits • ...